

cg12789488 PPP2R2D

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.6328 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:1e-04

cg22867714 VWF chr12:6165941-6166257 S_Shelf

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.1719 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:4e-04

cg06588028 LPAR5

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.7389 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:5e-04

cg02554391 CDKN1B chr12:12869798–12871248 S_Shore

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.9363 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:9e-04

cg00729708 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.8121 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.0477

cg21819984 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.0532 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.0241

cg26173375 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.0096 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.0056

cg21895387 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.9927 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.0035

cg06679270 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.2237 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0

cg06679270 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.2237 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0

cg25004981 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.843 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.1595

cg18388910 CERS3 chr15:101084428-101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.2579 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.0472

cg06777813 CERS3 chr15:101084428–101085178 Island

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.4953 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.1812

cg05983723 ST3GAL2

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.7016 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:9e-04

cg06270615 STAT3

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.5659 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:6e-04

cg03407524 FASN chr17:80046054–80046330 N_Shelf

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.5692 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0

cg04384638 GDF1;CERS1 chr19:19006031-19007546 S_Shore

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.408 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0.1635

cg14548901 ROCK2

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.1986 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:9e-04

cg02092276 COL6A6

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.2526 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:1e-04

cg05093818 MAPK10

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.253 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:0

cg01287079 FOXO3

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.3761 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:5e-04

cg24986615 PRKAR1B chr7:599089–599327 N_Shore

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.314 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:4e-04

cg03089725 FGFR1

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.3015 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:7e-04

cg14209823 GBGT1 chr9:136024223-136025112 S_Shelf

WSvsCTR p-value in GSE42865:0.1869 WSvsCTR p-value in this study:5e-04

